

Farming systems

Economics of upland rice-based cropping patterns for midhills of Uttar Pradesh

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We compared three rainfed spring rice-based and one June-seeded rice-based cropping patterns (200% cropping intensity) with traditional pattern (150% cropping intensity) in 1981-83 at Hawalbagh experimental farm (29°36' N, 70°40' E, elevation 1,250 m). The experiment used a randomized block design with six replications.

Soil was sandy loam with medium fertility. NPK were applied at 40-13-9 kg/ha to June-seeded rice and rapeseed *Brassica campestris* L. var Toria, 40-9-0 kg/ha to wheat and finger millet, 20-26-17 kg/ha to pea. Spring rice received 9-7 kg PK and 10 t farmyard manure/ha.

Grain yield, costs, and returns in 1981-83 for rainfed (upland), rice-based cropping systems in midhills of Uttar Pradesh, India.

Cropping pattern no. ^a	Components	Yield (t/ha)	Variable cost (\$/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Net return ^b (\$/ha)	Total net return (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost ratio
1	Jun-seeded rice (experimental strain) - wheat (VL 421)	1.9	199.6	373.0	22.1	226.9	1.6
2	Spring rice (VL 206) - pea for green fodder (VL 1)	2.8	173.4	320.9	204.8	187.9	1.6
3	Spring rice (VL 206) - rapeseed (T9)	2.4	197.8	338.9	83.6	184.5	1.5
4	Finger millet (VL 101) - fallow - spring rice (VL 206) - wheat (VL 421)	2.2	197.8	263.1 ^c	63.0	92.1 ^c	1.4
5	Spring rice (VL 206) - wheat (VL 421) - finger millet (VL 204) - rapeseed (T9)	0.8	141.1	335.2 ^c	121.5	197.3 ^c	1.6
		1.9	175.9		4.9		
		2.1	197.8		49.6		
		2.4	173.4		150.9		
		1.9	197.8		30.3		
		2.9	173.4		209.4		
		2.3	175.9		31.9		
		0.8	141.1		132.6		

^aCropping patterns 4 and 5 are 2-year rotations. ^bGross benefits — variable costs. ^cAfter discounted B:C; US \$1 = Rs 13.4.

Minimum turnaround between crops was 2 wk.

Highest rice yield was with spring rice (170 d duration) following fodder legume (see table). June-seeded rice (110 d duration) yielded almost as well, and the succeeding wheat crop yielded 2.8 t/ha.

Net returns were almost twice as high in the improved crop sequences as in the traditional cropping system. Highest average annual net return was with June-seeded rice - wheat. All intensive cropping sequences had higher benefit:cost ratios than the traditional 2-yr sequence. □

Yield of rice - oilseed cropping system without irrigation in coastal saline soil

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We studied rice varieties of different durations in the wet season (WS) followed by different oilseed crops in the dry season (DS) 1987-88 under nonirrigated condition in a coastal saline area where soil salinity increases in DS (EC of experimental plot 4.50-5.27 dS/m). Experimental plots were 28 m², with four replications.

Thirty-day-old seedlings of medium-duration IR56 and long-duration CR1009 were transplanted the third wk of Jul at 20- × 15-cm spacing. IR56 was harvested in Oct and CR1009 in Dec. Three oilseed crops—mustard (RJ3), linseed (local variety), and safflower

Yields of rice (1987) and oilseeds (1987-88) and rice - oilseed cropping system profitability.^a Motto, Orissa, India, 1987-88.

Cropping system	Yield (t/ha)		Net return ^b (\$/ha)	Net return per \$ investment
	Rice	Oil crop		
IR56 - mustard	3.2	0.3	350.18	1.23
IR56 - linseed	3.2	0.3	325.84	1.15
IR56 - safflower	3.2	0.5	417.60	1.47
CR1009 - mustard	3.6	0.3	427.84	1.50
CR1009 - linseed	3.6	0.3	400.75	1.41
CR1009 - safflower	3.6	0.5	478.74	1.68
Mean	3.4	0.4	400.16	1.40
LSD (P 0.05)	ns	0.1	43.11	—

^aCost of cultivation = \$284.64/ha. ^b\$1 = Rs 13.35.

(local variety) — were sown the first week of Dec in IR56 plots and the fourth week of Dec in CR1009 plots. All crops were grown without irrigation.

Soil had pH 6.60 with EC 0.35 dS/m in WS but pH 6.8 and EC 4.50 dS/m in Jan and pH 7.0 and EC 5.27 dS/m in Mar.

Rice yield was 3.2 t/ha for IR56 and 3.6 t/ha for CR1009 (see table).

Safflower had the significantly highest yield (0.5 t/ha) among the oilseed crops.

Net returns were significantly highest with CR1009 - safflower (\$478.74/ha). □

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